

Effect of Some Hydrazone Compounds on Corrosion Behaviour of Aluminium in Hydrochloric Acid and Sodium Hydroxide Solutions

AWAD I. AHMED, A. H. EL-ASKLANY and A. S. FOUDA

Department of Chemistry, Faculty of Science, Mansoura University, Mansoura, Egypt

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The inhibitive effect of some hydrazone compounds on the corrosion of aluminium in hydrochloric acid and sodium hydroxide solutions was studied by thermometric and weight loss methods. The adsorbability of inhibitor is dependent on the basicity of the oxygen, nitrogen and sulphur sites involved, and is independent of the chain length. The higher efficiencies of these compounds in acidic than in alkaline media may be due to the less negative potential of aluminium in hydrochloric acid solution, favouring adsorption of the added substances. Addition of Ca^{II} and Sr^{II} ions to the alkaline medium containing the hydrazone compounds increase the inhibition efficiency of the system.

RECENT studies¹⁻⁴ have shown that carbonyl compounds inhibit the corrosion of aluminium in hydrochloric acid solution. The same effect of hydrazide compounds has also been observed⁵ in inhibiting the corrosion of aluminium in acid solution. It has been reported⁶ that alkylamine and the corresponding alkylammonium ion act as corrosion inhibitors for aluminium dissolution in HCl and NaOH solutions. Polarization measurement⁷⁻⁹ on the organic compounds indicates that they are cathodic inhibitors. The adsorption of the organic compounds on the aluminium surface was shown^{8,9} to occur through their carbonyl group. The charge density residing on this group affects the inhibition efficiency^{1,2}. It has been reported¹⁰ that Ca^{II} ion can be used to improve the efficiency of some amino compounds in inhibiting the corrosion of Al in HCl and NaOH solutions. Also, Fouda¹¹ has observed the same effect of Ca^{II} ions in improving the efficiency of some β -diketo compounds used as inhibitors for the corrosion of Al in alkaline medium. The aim of this work was to investigate the role played by some hydrazone compounds in retarding the dissolution of Al in HCl and NaOH solutions employing the thermometric technique developed by Mylius^{1,2} and weight-loss methods⁴. The effect of Sr^{II} and Ca^{II} ions on the efficiency of these compounds was also examined.

Experimental

Stock solutions of HCl (2 M), NaOH (2 M), SrCl_2 (0.03%), CaCl_2 (0.03%), degreasing mixture and additives were prepared. The used compounds are not easily hydrolysed in the HCl or NaOH solution under the experimental conditions. The chemical composition of the aluminium sheet used was Al, 99.525; Si, 0.150; Fe, 0.190; Mn, 0.005; Mg, 0.100; Cu, 0.030, and the dimension of the

test pieces were $1 \times 10 \times 0.5$ cm. The sheets were degreased and cleaned as described elsewhere⁴. The reaction vessel used was basically the same as described by Mylius^{1,2}, in which the variation in the temperature of the system is measured to $\pm 0.05^\circ$ as a function of time.

The reaction number (RN) is defined as, $\text{RN} = T_m - T_i / t^\circ\text{C min}^{-1}$, where T_m and T_i are the maximum and initial temperatures, respectively and t is the time in minutes taken to reach T_m . The efficiency of a given inhibitor was evaluated as the percentage reduction in RN,

$$\frac{(\text{RN})_{\text{free}} - (\text{RN})_{\text{inh}}}{(\text{RN})_{\text{free}}} \times 100$$

where $(\text{RN})_{\text{free}}$ and $(\text{RN})_{\text{inh}}$ are the reaction numbers of aluminium dissolution in free acid or base and in the presence of the given inhibitor, respectively.

The inhibition efficiency of the compounds was computed from the loss in weight according to, $(W_{\text{free}} - W_{\text{inh}} / W_{\text{free}}) \times 100$, where W is the loss in weight of the test piece.

Results and Discussion

The loss in weight of aluminium strips in 2 M HCl and 2 M NaOH in the absence and in the presence of 10^{-2} M 4-phenyl-1-GP-3-thiosemicarbazide (I), methyl isopropyl ketone (II), acetylacetone (III), butaraldehyde (IV) and methyl ethyl ketone-*N*-cyanoacetylhydrazone (V) compounds was determined. The weight loss is plotted as a function of time (Fig. 1). The inhibition efficiency data of these additives after 60 min are included in Table 1. The order of increasing inhibition efficiency of these compounds in 2 M HCl and 2 M NaOH is $\text{I} > \text{II} > \text{V} > \text{III} > \text{IV}$.

Fig. 1. Weight loss-time curves for all inhibitors used at concentration 0.01 M: (1) free acid, (2) IV, (3) III, (4) V, (5) II and (6) I.

Inhibitor	Inhibition %	
	2 M HCl	2 M NaOH
I	88.4	75.7
II	72.0	52.9
III	61.5	30.6
IV	50.0	24.7
V	67.6	49.3

Temperature change of the system involving Al in 2 M HCl and 2 M NaOH was followed in absence and in presence of different inhibitor concentrations (Fig. 2 a, b). The maximum temperature measured in the acid solution is 61.8°, and is attained after 22 min. This corresponds to a reaction number (RN) of 1.74 °C min⁻¹. The dissolution of the metal in the basic solution is somewhat slower. T_m amounts to 79° but is reached after 46 min, the RN is 1.23 °C min⁻¹. On increasing the concentration of the additives the time required to reach T_m increases. This indicates that the additives retard the dissolution of aluminium in both the media, presumably

Fig. 2a. Temperature-time curves for all inhibitors used at concentration 10⁻³ M in 2 M HCl: (1) free acid, (2) IV, (3) III, (4) V, (5) II and (6) I.

Fig 2b. Temperature-time curves for all inhibitors used at concentration $10^{-3} M$ in $2 M NaOH$: (1) free alkali, (2) IV, (3) III, (4) V, (5) II and (6) I.

by their adsorption on the surface of the metal. The extent of retardation or inhibition depends on the degree of coverage of the metal with the adsorbate, and the temperature-time curves provide a means of differentiating between weak and strong adsorption⁴. Strong adsorption is noted in acid medium for all hydrazone derivatives studied, since a simultaneous increase in t and a diminution in T_m take place, and both the factors cause a larger decrease in the reaction number (RN) of the system. Weak adsorption is noted in alkaline solution. The results recorded in Table 2 reveal that the efficiency of corrosion inhibition as determined from the percentage reduction in RN varies with the type of the hydrazone derivatives in $2 M HCl$ and $2 M NaOH$, respectively. The inhibi-

TABLE 2—EFFICIENCY OF CORROSION INHIBITION AS DETERMINED BY PERCENTAGE REDUCTION IN RN AT $10^{-3} M$

Inhibitor	Reduction % in RN	
	$2 M HCl$	$2 M NaOH$
I	91.2	77.9
II	71.0	54.1
III	63.5	32.4
IV	52.0	25.5
V	65.6	48.0

tion efficiency of the compounds increases in the order, $IV < III < V < II < I$. The points of inflexion in the percentage inhibition vs concentration curves (Fig. 3) for the hydrazone derivatives occurs at

Fig. 3. Inhibition % - concentration curves for all inhibitors used: (1) I, (2) II, (3) V, (4) III and (5) IV.

$C = 10 \times 10^{-4} M$ and bears no relation to their chain length. The curves in Fig. 3 are, in fact, similar to adsorption isotherms. The value of C at which the percentage inhibition starts to change slowly with concentration may be taken to occur near to the completion of a monolayer. Compound III is the only exception and gives curve with two inflexion points, indicating that two-step adsorption takes place. Compound I has a relatively large molecular weight (volume) and like other similar surface active compounds⁴, is capable of giving a single adsorbed layer. Plots of the time delay $\log \Delta t$ vs $\log C$ confirm the above explanation (Fig. 4).

Fig. 4. Variation of $\log \Delta t$ with $\log C$ for all inhibitors used: (1) I, (2) II, (3) V, (4) III and (5) IV.

Hassan *et al.*⁸ obtained similar curves for some β -diketo compounds. In this manner, the present results indicate that the adsorption of the organic compounds on the metal surface would take place through functional groups, essentially the $C=S$, $C=O$ and $C=N$. Owing the fact that sulphur is a stronger Lewis base than oxygen and nitrogen, compound I is assumed to be first adsorbed through the $C=S$ group leading to a reduction in the dissolution rates. As the bulk concentration and correspondingly the surface coverage is increased electron donation from $C=O$ group sets in and the RN decreases with concentration. Thereafter adsorption occurs through both $C=S$ and $C=O$ groups with the aromatic rings projecting in the solution side¹⁴. Accordingly, compound I exhibits the highest adsorption tendency. In compounds II, IV and V containing the $-N$ -cyanoacetylhydrazone group, thus the reduction in the RN resulting from the adsorption of the carbonyl group is the same. The difference in the efficiencies would depend essentially on the charge density of $C=N$. The magnitude of the

latter should depend on the electron repelling character of the substituent in the α -position. $N=C(CH_3)CH(CH_3)CH_3$ is more basic than $N=C(CH_3)CH_2CH_3 > N=CH-CH_2-CH_2-CH_3$. Although compound III has two carbonyl groups in addition to $N=C$ group, its basicity is affected by the presence of hydrogen bonding.

The order of inhibition of the compounds used in acidic and alkaline media are the same, $I > II > V > III > IV$. The observed higher efficiency of these compounds in acidic than in alkaline medium may be due to the less negative potential of aluminium in the former, favouring adsorption of the added substances^{10,15}.

The same order of inhibitive action is obtained by weight-loss and thermometric measurements. This indicates the validity of the results of the thermometric method as a simple and rapid way for determining and comparing inhibition efficiencies of additives.

Effect of Ca^{II} and Sr^{II} ions on the corrosion inhibition of Al in 2 M NaOH solution: Weight-loss technique was used to examine the effect of Ca^{II} and Sr^{II} ions on the corrosion inhibition of aluminium in 2 M NaOH in absence and in presence of the hydrazone derivatives. Table 3 gives the percentage inhibition brought about by 0.03% of these cations. From the results obtained it was found that Sr^{II} gives higher efficiency than Ca^{II} . This may be due to the higher atomic weight of Sr than Ca and on the basis of their basicity which increases with the increase in atomic weights.

TABLE 3—EFFECT OF Sr^{II} AND Ca^{II} IONS ON THE INHIBITIVE EFFICIENCY OF HYDRAZONE COMPOUNDS AT $10^{-3} M$

Additive	Inhibition %	
	(a)	(b)
$SrCl_2$	—	56.8
I + $SrCl_2$	60.0	76.1
II + $SrCl_2$	40.1	66.2
III + $SrCl_2$	25.5	45.5
IV + $SrCl_2$	20.3	44.4
V + $SrCl_2$	43.9	62.9
$CaCl_2$	—	45.3
I + $CaCl_2$	60.0	70.3
II + $CaCl_2$	40.1	62.2
III + $CaCl_2$	25.5	40.1
IV + $CaCl_2$	20.3	36.6
V + $CaCl_2$	43.9	58.9

(a) In absence of cations. (b) In presence of cations.

It is also observed (Table 3) that the inhibition efficiency of the inhibitors increases in the presence of Ca^{II} and Sr^{II} ions. This may be due to the fact that these ions are chemisorbed on the aluminium surface¹⁶. The presence of Ca^{II} and Sr^{II} ions in the medium aids in bringing negatively charged species inclusive of the aluminate ion closer to the metal surface, thus enhancing inhibition, as has actually been observed.

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